

Dealing with the Digital Care Gap

Automation is not a solution to the gender care gap at home

Background and Vision

- Smart home technologies do not reduce or eliminate traditional care work or domestic chores.
- On the contrary, they create new forms of labor in the form of digital housekeeping – tasks like setup, maintenance, troubleshooting, and data management.
- These technologies can also reinforce gendered dependencies and inequalities, and introduce new risks of control and surveillance within the home.
- Therefore, technological innovation must be accompanied by social and policy measures that promote equality, transparency, and user empowerment.

How Can I Get Involved?

Building Owners, Manufacturers, and Technology

EU Member States

Researchers & National Statistics Offices

Educators, Schools & NGOs

Design with gender equality in mind:

- When developing digital home technologies, consider the unequal division of labor within households.
- Do not assume that all users have technical expertise, free time, or equal decision-making power.
- Inclusive design means creating systems that are accessible, intuitive, and easy to share among household members with varying skill levels.

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Run inclusive focus groups and co-design workshops with women from diverse households:

- Systematically invite primary household managers to share everyday pain points, unmet needs, and desired outcomes.
- Incorporate these insights directly into product roadmaps so that new technologies genuinely reduce unpaid domestic work and improve the quality of life for all household members.

Policy recommendation: Regulate smart home manufacturers to prevent power imbalances within households

- Policymakers should require companies to implement transparency features, shared access, and user-friendly control settings to minimize the risks of surveillance, misuse, and internal power asymmetries in domestic spaces.

Update time-use and digitalization studies to include digital housekeeping:

Surveys should capture:

- How homes are digitalized.
- The actual time spent managing digital devices and infrastructures – a growing, often invisible part of domestic labor.
- The gender dimensions of domestic work and digital housekeeping.

Promote inclusive digital education:

- Women and other marginalized groups need targeted, accessible training in digital skills to ensure more equitable participation in technical household responsibilities and decision-making.
- Empowering all household members digitally is key to closing the digital care gap.

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